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Issues of Interaction between BRICS and RCEP in the Framework of Global Economic Integration

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Studying the issues of BRICS and RCEP integration is relevant, since in a changing world economy with traditional centers of power losing their dominant role, the integration of these associations can become an important factor for the formation of new economic and political alliances.

The article aims to analyze and discuss the issues arising in the interaction of coalitions (BRICS and RCEP) in the context of global economic integration.

Materials and methods. The materials were publications in peer-reviewed journals on international relations, economics and political science (Environmental Science and Pollution Research, etc.), official documents and reports: reports and documents published by the BRICS, RCEP and other international organizations.

Results. The authors analyzed data on trade turnover between the BRICS countries and the rest of the world, as well as the share of trade of the member countries within the framework of the association from their total trade turnover. The analysis of the trade turnover of the RCEP countries as of 2019 (in billions of US dollars) showed that the bulk of the foreign trade of the RCEP member countries is with other countries that are members of the association; notably, China is the largest partner for most of the bloc's states.

For the majority of countries, the share of foreign trade with other residents of the EMEA is more than 50%, which indicates a high degree of developed trade relations and integration between them. The exceptions are China (intra-bloc trade share of 30%), which is explained by the scale of the Chinese economy itself and its foreign trade links; Singapore (42%), which comes from its specialization in services and financial activities; and Japan (47%), the level of which is quite close to that of other countries in the bloc. Thus, the average level of intra-bloc trade is about 44%. Consequently, the countries' relations are very strong and reflect their desire to deepen integration and develop the economies of the region.

Conclusion. The trade relations within the BRICS-RCEP interaction are at a very advanced level and further transit to a higher level of integration.

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INTRODUCTION

Studying the integration of BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) and RCEP (Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership) is relevant, since in a changing world economy with traditional centers of power losing their dominant role, the integration of these associations can become an important factor for the formation of new economic and political alliances. Notably, this integration offers opportunities for cooperation in areas such as trade, investment, technology and sustainable development, which can lead to mutually beneficial outcomes.

Thus, studying BRICS and RCEP integration is important for understanding current trends in international relations and economics.

We have highlighted a number of publications that can help further understand the dynamics of BRICS and RCEP integration and their impact on international relations and economy.

P. Sang believes that the global financial crisis of 2008 caused the emergence of a new global economic order and governance which were realized in new economic associations (G7, G20 and BRICS) [1].

According to J. Kakkunen, the BRICS can become the basis of a new world order – a polycentric world order in which the key elements are different types and forms of regions. The author believes that today BRICS is an alliance of like-minded people trying to reform the existing liberal world order. BRICS as a case of multiple and diverse but cross-cutting cooperation could become a ‘bridge’ between the global and regional worlds: each BRICS member is also a leading economy in its region and can actively develop regional integration [2].

Shi He et al. believe that cross-country synchronization of business cycles and BRICS trade integration looks inconclusive at the moment. The authors believe there are two possible ways to promote BRICS regional economic integration: conclusion of a regional trade agreement (RTA) and adoption of a central bank digital currency (CBDC) [3].

C. Shameem and K. Jayaprasad analyze the BRICS from both political and economic perspectives. The authors write that physical and geographical proximity is often seen as a cause of conflict between countries which can be radically resolved by forming economic ties. Strong economic relations between BRICS countries reduce the likelihood of conflict, creating the possibility of a peaceful global atmosphere. Globalization, trade liberalization, transnationalism and privatization create a favorable space for BRICS [4].

According to M. Jakovljevic et al., the leading emerging markets of BRICS countries are increasingly shaping the supply and demand landscape of the global market, particularly in the health sector for medical goods and services. The BRICS share of global health expenditure and future projections (up to 2030) will play a prominent role in the 2020s [5].

The Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (the 'free trade area plus' agreement) was signed in Hanoi on November 15, 2020 and entered into force on January 1, 2022, creating the world's largest free trade zone.

C. Wang critically analyzes the legal provisions that led India to withdraw their FTAA, the possibility of isolationism that India may face, and the geopolitical changes in Sino-Indian relations after the COVID-19 pandemic. The author argues that unbalanced economic relations, India's self-sufficient ideology, and China's growing hegemony in the Asia-Pacific region are some of the major factors why India abandoned RCEP [6].

Y. Guo et al. study the impact of natural resource rents on international trade of RCEP members. Their results emphasize the important role of natural resource rents, geopolitical risk, GDP and energy efficiency in forming international trade patterns within the trade block of the RCEP. The authors substantiated the detrimental effect of oil rents on international trade [7].

Kejuan Sun et al. analyze more substantively and show a significant expansion of bilateral trade between member countries with trade agreements only through the RCEP, with trade in intermediate goods stimulating more than final goods for most member countries. Participation between member countries increased in textiles, apparel, automobiles, and food. The financial and pharmaceutical sectors experienced an increase in direct participation in both member and non-member countries [8].

K. Bipin studies the role of the BRICS countries in the formation of regional (free) trade agreements; in particular, the author assesses the impact on the BRICS countries of other coalitions: the Trans-Pacific Partnership and the RCEP [9].

Thus, issues arise in both coalitions, requiring analysis and discussion, both in BRICS and RCEP within the framework of global economic integration, which served as the purpose of our study. In particular, it concerns the issues of environmental pollution and the development of a green economy.

Hassan et al. claim responsibility for climate change and environmental degradation partly lies with the trade union of the WREP [10]. According to N. Apergis et al., foreign direct investment flowing from developed to developing countries can increase carbon emissions in developing countries because the latter are seen as pollution havens due to their lenient environmental regulations. According to the authors, BRICS countries should promote net foreign direct investment flows by reducing environmental damage, and investor countries should be evaluated based on environmental damage in host countries [11].

Y. Tang investigates the impact of ICT diffusion and financial development to achieve green economic growth in BRICS economies. Internet development has a positive impact on green growth in four BRICS economies except India [12].

Z. Zia found that environmental degradation slowed down in developed economies due to more sustainable environmental regulations, advances in technology and better institutions. In BRISC countries, according to the authors, institutional reforms and more spending on green technologies are needed in the long run to ensure a sustainable future [13].

Thus, the scientific problem of BRICS and RCEP integration lies in the complexities and contradictions that arise when trying to bring together countries with different economic, political and cultural contexts. The main aspects of this problem include:

Economic Inequalities: Differences in the level of economic development and resource base of BRICS countries can create imbalances in integration and create resentment among participants.

Diversity of interests: The BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) have different economic models, political systems and foreign economic priorities which may complicate development of harmonized strategies.

Political differences: Internal and external political conflicts among the BRICS countries may hinder effective cooperation and integration within the RCEP framework.

These aspects create a complex research problem that requires in-depth analysis and an interdisciplinary approach to understand the dynamics of BRICS and RCEP integration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials for studying the issues of interaction of BRICS and RCEP organizations within the framework of global economic integration were publications in peer-reviewed journals on international relations, economics and political science, such as Environmental Science and Pollution Research, International Organizations Research Journal, A TWQ Journal, Applied Economics, American Review of Political Economy, Pacific Focus, Resources Policy, Journal of Asian Economics and others.

Papers on specific aspects of BRICS and RCEP; books on international integration, economics and BRICS grouping; collections of articles on international organizations and regional integrations; official documents and reports published by the BRICS Group, RCEP and other international organizations were also used as sources.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The authors of the article analyzed the World Bank's WITS trade statistics data, namely, data on trade turnover between the RCEP member countries and the rest of the world, as well as

the share of trade of the member countries within the association of their total trade turnover. The analysis of the trade turnover of the RCEP countries as of 2019 (in billion USD) showed that the bulk of foreign trade of the RCEP member countries is accounted for by other countries that are members of the association; notably, China is the largest partner for the majority of the bloc's states [14].

This relationship can be clearly seen in Figure 1.

Notes: Blue – within RCEP; Red – between other countries

Figure 1 Ratio of foreign trade within the bloc and with other countries for 2019 (in %)

Figure 1 shows that for the majority of countries, the share of foreign trade with other residents of the EMEP is more than 50%, which indicates a high degree of trade relations and

integration between them. The exceptions are China (the share of intra-bloc trade is 30%), which is explained by the scale of the Chinese economy and its foreign trade ties; Singapore (42%), which is due to its specialization in services and foreign trade relations; and Japan (47%), which is quite close to the other countries in the bloc. Thus, the average level of intra-bloc trade is about 44%. Thus, the countries' relations are very strong and reflect their desire to deeper integration and development of the region's economies.

When analyzing the trade relations of the RCEP, the largest export and import partners of the bloc's member states are to be considered. This allows assessing trade relations with individual states and their place in the foreign trade of the association, as well as determining which states are strategic partners according to these criteria and the degree of dependence on these states.

The analysis revealed that the largest partners of the RCEP member states are China, a member of the partnership, and the United States, a non-resident. These states are both the largest exporters and importers for the region. Of the non-affiliated states with extensive trade ties, Germany and India, and to a lesser extent Saudi Arabia and the UK, are also worth noting; these countries are both exporters and importers of the bloc's various goods. Among the resident countries, Malaysia, Japan, Thailand, Singapore and South Korea, the most developed countries in the region, also stand out to some extent. In general, the GEM has large-scale trade relations between the countries that make up the bloc, which makes it possible to maintain independence from other countries in the functioning of industrial production, but there is a single non-resident state that can exert a certain influence on the domestic economies of the countries through changes in the supply of certain goods (intermediate consumption).

Reducing the dependence of the whole bloc's economy on other countries in this aspect requires intensifying trade turnover between its members and expanding the range of supplies, which, in turn, may require expanding investment in R&D to create high-tech parts and units, products, implementing various joint projects in the field of infrastructure, etc., and further expanding customs regulation benefits Figure 2 shows the change in trade turnover of the participants of the RCEP in recent years.

According to Figure 2, mainly the trade turnover within the framework of RCEP is decreasing, which can be justified by the spread of COVID-19 which caused disruption of global supply chains and of industrial complexes all over the world, especially affecting the countries whose fiscal revenues are heavily dependent on foreign economic activity. Nevertheless, the decline is not significant, though the impact on the ASEAN countries, Japan and South Korea is slightly stronger than on Australia and New Zealand. China, the largest supplier of various components and parts on a world level, already entered a stage of recovery of its activity and is functioning normally.

Notes: 1 – ASEAN; 2 – Australia; 3 – China; 4 – New Zealand; 5 – South Korea; 5 – Japan

Figure 2 Dynamics of trade turnover within the framework of the All-Russian Economic Partnership in 2018-2020 (in million USD) [15]

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Therefore, trade relations within the RCEP are at a very advanced level and contribute to further transit to a higher level of integration. With the share of domestic trade at 44%, there is a strong basis for further deepening of relations in all areas. RCEP is self-sufficient in this aspect.

The political situation in them today remains multidirectional, because polarization of the world in the course of Russia's SWOT in Ukraine disturbed the usual course of things, and the influence of both the US and China in this region is not fully formalized, although it remains confrontational and strives to defend its leadership in the management of the Asia-Pacific region.

The battle for the RCEP and true cooperation with the member countries is only gaining momentum, that is why it is necessary to take into account the BRICS experience and find our place under the sun in the projects of the countries of the region and in access to the chains of interaction and cooperation with those states that today are increasingly dependent

on hydrocarbon raw materials or need our agricultural support, other unique resources with which today Russia can organize a victorious chess game, transferring the zugswang of the West into our rapid endgame with Chinese partners in mechanisms in the Asia-Pacific region.

Thus, the prospects for BRICS and RCEP integration depend on the following factors:

Sustained economic growth: If the BRICS countries can demonstrate sustained economic growth and development, this may create a more favorable environment for integration.

Addressing political differences: Reducing political tensions and resolving conflicts among BRICS countries can facilitate more effective cooperation.

Establishing institutional arrangements: Developing clear mechanisms and institutions for BRICS countries to coordinate their actions within the RCEP framework can facilitate the integration process.

Overall, while BRICS and RCEP integration faces certain challenges, there are also opportunities for its development, especially if there is political will and a strategic approach.

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